

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON IMPACT-INDUCED DAMAGE IN CFRP LAMINATED COMPOSITES USING SAM AND SEM TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Impact tests by an air-gun type impact machine were undertaken on a series of CFRP laminated specimens with different ply orientations of $[0_6/\theta_{10}/0_6]$. The tests were conducted under the conditions of same impact velocity of 60m/s and same impact energy level of 2J for two steel impactor balls with different diameters. A scanning acoustic microscope (SAM) revealed the delamination damage at specified interfaces and a scanning electron microscope (SEM) some transverse cracks in the form of matrix crackings or fiber/matrix debondings at the cross-sectional area. On the basis of microscopic examinations of these interior damage, the initiation and propagation mechanisms of the impact-induced damage were discussed.

Key words: CFRP Laminates, Impact-induced Damage, CAI, Air-gun Type Impact Machine, Scanning Acoustic Microscope, Scanning Electron Microscope

1. INTRODUCTION

The impact-induced damage is the worst type of damage for carbon fiber reinforced composites[1]. In particular, delamination damage caused by the impact loading is known to produce significant reductions in the residual compression strength of CFRP laminated composites (CAI strength), which is a major problem associated with the structural integrity of composite compression components. Much effort has therefore been devoted to the study of the effects of impact-induced damage on the load-bearing capacities of these components in the last two decades[2-6]. In the course of these studies, attempts have also been made to investigate the damage mechanisms[7-14]. Only a few detailed studies, however, have been reported on the damage initiation and propagation mechanisms of CFRP laminated composites, and more work is still required to understand them well. This paper reports the results of microscopic examinations of the delamination damage and transverse cracks detected through a scanning acoustic microscope and a scanning electron microscope, from which the initiation and propagation mechanisms of the impact-induced damage were discussed.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Composite Fabrication

The test specimens studied were manufactured from pre-impregnated sheets of KASEI Fiberite HYEJ12. The tensile strength of carbon fibers in the UD prepregs is 4.22–4.27 GPa and Young's modulus 231–233 GPa. These prepregs are layed up to 22 plies in the stacking sequence of $[0_6/\theta_{10}/0_6]$, where θ denotes the angle of fiber orientation inclined to a longitudinal direction 0 of the laminate panels. An autoclave moulding technique was used to process the laminate panels. The panels were heated up to 130 °C under the consolidation pressure of 3 atm and then the mould was kept for 60 min. After the mould was removed, the panels were cut into test specimens. The laminate test specimens have the dimension of 180 mm by 100 mm and the average thickness was 2.8 mm. In the experiment 6 kinds of laminate specimens were used, each of which was characterized by the angle θ as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Test specimens and stacking sequence

Specimen	Stacking sequence
C15	$0_6/15_{10}/0_6$
C30	$0_6/30_{10}/0_6$
C45	$0_6/45_{10}/0_6$
C60	$0_6/60_{10}/0_6$
C75	$0_6/75_{10}/0_6$
C90	$0_6/90_{10}/0_6$

2.2 Impact Test Procedure

Impact tests were performed using an air-gun type impact machine as shown schematically in Figure 1. Air was bled from a supply line into a cylindrical reservoir. Two kinds of steel balls 5 mm and 10 mm in diameter were used as the impactors. The steel balls were accelerated by compressed air discharged from the reservoir. The impact machine had a velocity measuring device at the end of the gun barrel. As the steel ball traveled through this device, laser beams emitted by photodiodes were interrupted and an electronic counter was triggered. The impact velocity was calculated from the distance between the photodiodes and the time intervals between beam interruptions. The impact velocity was controlled by adjusting the air pressure in the reservoir. Meanwhile, the test specimens were mounted in the fixture during testing and the edges were clamped by the frames. In the impact test, the specimens were damaged by the steel impactor ball propelled normal to the center of the surface at the desired impact velocities or energy levels.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of air gun type impact machine

2.3 Test Conditions

The specimens were impacted under two different test conditions. Firstly, both steel balls 5 mm (0.5g) and 10 mm(4.1g) in diameter were propelled at the same velocity of 60 m/s. Secondly, while a 5 mm-diameter steel ball was accelerated at a velocity of 90 m/s, a 10 mm steel ball was at 30 m/s, which produced the same kinetic energy, i.e., the same impact energy of 2J.

3. MICROSCOPIC EXAMINATIONS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Delamination Damage Characterization

The impact damaged specimens were ultrasonically inspected using a scanning acoustic microscope (SAM), Olympus UH Pulse 100. The C-scans revealed the delamination damage clearly at specified interfaces; interface A and B. Interface A is one between 6th and 7th plies, and interface B between 16th and 17 plies, at which a major change in the fiber orientation occurs. The former is located nearer to the front surface (impacted surface) of the specimen and the latter to the back surface (opposite the impacted surface). Figure 2 shows typical delamination patterns of the test specimen impacted by the 5 mm diameter steel ball at a velocity of 60 m/s. The damage zones have characteristic two-lobed shape long in the preferred directions, i.e., at interface A, extended mainly in the θ -deg ply direction, while at interface B, in the 0-deg ply direction. The damage was confined locally to the areas centered at the impact location, which suggests that the delamination damage is due to the bending-induced stresses. The effects of ply angle θ on the delamination areas were shown in Figure 3 for the 5 mm steel balls. The delamination area increases with an increased ply angle θ , and the increasing rate is remarkably higher at interface B than at interface A. The delamination areas are also related to the size of steel impactor balls in Figure 4. A 10 mm steel ball exhibits more increase in delamination area than a 5

Figure 2. SAM photograph of delamination damage (5mm steel ball, 60m/s)

Figure 3. Delamination area vs. ply angle

Figure 4. Effect of impactor size on delamination area

Figure 5. SAM photographs of delamination damage (10mm steel ball, 30m/s)

Table 2. Delamination area

Specimen	D=5mm, V=90m/s		D=10mm, V=30m/s		Delamination area ratio	
	Interface A SA5	Interface B SB5	Interface A SA10	Interface B SB10	SA5/SA10	SB5/SB10
C30	57.0	256.9	---	40.9	---	6.3
C45	68.1	421.8	31.0	330.0	2.2	1.3
C60	93.1	511.3	26.5	255.2	3.5	2.0
C90	121.4	669.6	42.5	353.7	2.9	1.9

(Average): (2.9) (1.7)

■₅, ■₁₀:mass of steel balls

v₅, v₁₀:impact velocity of steel balls

■₅v₅²/2=■₁₀v₁₀²/2=2J(same impact energy condition)

$$v_5/v_{10} = \sqrt{m_{10}/m_5} = \sqrt{4.1/0.5} = 2.9$$

$$\sqrt{v_5/v_{10}} = 1.7$$

mm one when impacted at the same velocity. On the other hand, Figure 5 shows the C-scanned delamination damage impacted at an energy level of 2J for the 10 mm steel balls. The damage patterns and features are similar to Figure 2. The delamination areas measured using an image processing technique are summarized in Table 2. If the impact energies are same for each steel ball, a smaller size impactor with higher velocity tends to produce greater delamination damage. The ratios of the delamination areas (5 mm to 10 mm steel balls) at each interface are also given in Table 2. The delamination area ratio at interface A is higher than that at interface B, and it should be noted that the averages for the three specimens were very close to the values calculated from v_5/v_{10} and $\sqrt{v_5/v_{10}}$, respectively.

3.2 Transverse Cracks Characterization

To further examine the interior damage, the impacted specimens were sectioned through the specimen thickness at different locations and inspected using a scanning electron microscope (SEM). Figure 6 reveals optically-observed cross sections of the specimens damaged at an impact velocity of 60 m/s, which were cut along the 90-deg ply direction, (a) through the impact point and (b) away from it. A section passing through the center of impact has more damage than that otherwise. The damage patterns visible in the cross sections are characterized by three kinds of transverse cracks: horizontal, oblique and vertical cracks. Figure 7 shows SEM photograph of the cross section along the 90-deg ply direction through the impact point for the specimens impacted by the 10 mm steel ball. The horizontal cracks correspond to the delamination and therefore it can be found

that small delamination occurred in the specimen as well as two distinct delaminations at interface A and B inspected by SAM. Figure 8 shows micrographs of the cross section along the 0-deg ply direction for the specimen impacted by the 5 mm steel ball. Oblique cracks are observed between interface A and B, where some initiate from interface A and others propagate toward interface B to hit. Careful examination of the magnified micrograph indicates that these oblique cracks are of matrix shear type and found in the form of matrix crackings or fiber/matrix debondings. Vertical cracks are also seen mainly between interface B and the back surface as shown in Figure 9. After initiated from the back surface and at the point opposite the center of impact probably due to the greater tensile stresses, vertical cracks propagate toward the interface B to hit, at which the delamination is created. Vertical cracks are greatly associated with the delamination onset at interface B. On the other hand, Figure 10 shows a typical example of SEM photographs of the specimens damaged at the same impact energy of 2J. It can be found that transverse crackings are more pronounced when impacted at a higher velocity and by a smaller size impactor than when otherwise.

Figure 6. Optical micrographs of cross sections along 90° ply direction (10mm steel ball, 60m/s)

Figure 7. SEM photograph of cross section along 90° ply direction through impact point (X35, 10mm steel ball, 60m/s)

The oblique cracks detected between the front surface and interface A initiate near from the center of impact and propagate toward the interface A to hit. It can be expected from the data that they are dominantly associated with the delamination onset at interface A. The damage patterns and features other than these are similar to those discussed in the same impact velocity case.

4. CONCLUSIONS

CFRP laminated composite specimens with simple stacking sequence of $[0_6/\theta_{10}/0_6]$ were impulsively damaged by 5 mm and 10 mm diameter steel impactor balls under the test conditions of same impact velocity of 60 m/s and same impact energy level of 2J. After impact testing, the damaged specimens were microscopically inspected using SAM and SEM techniques to examine the damage initiation and propagation mechanisms. The microscopic examinations could provide useful insight into the damage induced in the specimens. Although the number of tests conducted was limited, the following conclusions may be drawn:

1. The interior damage was characterized by delamination and transverse crackings.

Figure 8. SEM photographs of cross section along 0° ply direction (X50, X1000, 5mm steel ball, 60m/s)

Figure 9. SEM photographs of cross section along 90° ply direction (X130, X1000, 5mm steel ball, 60m/s)

2. The delamination damage was detected clearly at two distinct interfaces, at which a major change in the ply angles occurred.
3. The damage zones have characteristic two-lobed shape long in the θ -deg ply direction at interface A (nearer to the impacted surface), while in the 0-deg ply direction at interface B (nearer to the back surface opposite the impacted surface).
4. Transverse crackings through the specimen thickness were observed in the cross sections and these are classified into horizontal, oblique and vertical cracks in the form of matrix crackings or fiber/matrix debondings.
5. Horizontal cracks parallel to the specimen surfaces were found to correspond to the delamination damage detected by SAM.
6. Oblique cracks detected mainly between interface A and B, and between interface A and the impacted surface, were more or less associated with the delamination onset at interface A.
7. Vertical cracks were detected mainly between interface B and the back surface, and they were expected to be greatly associated with the delamination onset at interface B.
8. From a quantitative examination of delamination area, the extent of delamination damage was found to be remarkably influenced by the size of steel impactor balls and the impact velocity.

Figure 10. SEM photographs of cross section along 90° ply direction through impact point(X35, C45, same impact energy of 2J)

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